

Original Research

Effect of Fixture Release Timing in Butt Welding on Deformation and Residual Stress of High-Speed Train Sidewalls

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Abstract

A partially butt-welded 6005A aluminum alloy sidewall structure of a high-speed train was selected as the research object, and a thermo-mechanical sequential coupled finite element model considering the clamp constraint and release process was established. The post-weld deformation and residual stress distributions under four working conditions—free condition (FC), continuously clamped condition (CC), immediate release condition (IR), and release after cooling to 100°C (TR)—were compared and analyzed. The results show that, under the condition of consistent welding temperature field distribution, the timing of clamp release mainly affects the post-weld mechanical response. Under all four working conditions, the out-of-plane deformation of the component is mainly negative displacement. The continuous constraint working condition has the most obvious inhibitory effect on the out-of-plane deformation after welding. In contrast, the release working conditions all show a certain degree of spring back effect after the clamp is released. The longitudinal residual stresses under all four conditions show the typical distribution characteristics of tensile stress concentration in the weld center area and gradually transforming into compressive stress away from the weld area. The peak value order is CC > IR > TR > FC. For transverse residual stress, the CC condition maintains a higher tensile stress level along the weld direction, which is significantly higher than the other working conditions. Studies have shown that the timing of clamp release essentially alters the distribution relationship between deformation release and stress retention during welding shrinkage. Appropriately extending the clamp holding time helps to achieve a better balance between post-weld deformation control and residual stress reduction.

Keywords: high-speed train sidewall; butt welding; timing of fixture release; residual stress; welding deformation

Introduction

High-speed train sidewalls are typical large-scale thin-walled aluminum alloy welded structures. Due to their low stiffness and high thermal sensitivity, welding often leads to significant deformation, residual stress, and springback, which seriously affect dimensional accuracy and assembly quality.

Many researchers have investigated these problems from different perspectives. Li et al. reviewed the effects of residual stress on the manufacturing of aluminum alloy structural panels and pointed out that residual stress is a key factor affecting deformation and dimensional stability[1]. Zhou et al. studied high-strength aluminum alloy thin plates and showed that appropriate process control can effectively reduce welding residual stress and distortion[2]. Zhao et al. further demonstrated that welding direction and welding sequence have significant effects on distortion and residual stress in aluminum alloy structures[3].

The role of external constraint has also been widely discussed. Raftar et al. found that clamping conditions have an important influence on welding-induced deformation and residual stress in 6082 aluminum alloy[4]. Sarmast et al. analyzed the relationship among residual stress, microstructural evolution, and mechanical response during welding, further clarifying the thermo-mechanical behavior of heat-treatable aluminum alloys[5].

In addition, prediction methods for thin-walled structures have been continuously improved. Grams proposed a new method for predicting welding residual stress and distortion[6]. Ma et al. established a deformation prediction model for hollow thin-walled aluminum alloy structural parts under coupled loading conditions[7]. Zhang et al. investigated welding deformation in hollow thin-walled complex structures[8], and Ma et al. further predicted welding deformation and residual stress of hollow thin-walled aluminum alloy parts based on the inherent strain method[9].

Although considerable progress has been made, existing studies mainly focus on welding sequence, heat input, constraint intensity, and deformation prediction. Previous studies on welding constraints have mainly focused on constraint conditions and their effects on welding deformation and residual stress. However, the influence of fixture release timing during cooling remains unclear, especially for butt-welded high-speed train sidewall structures. Therefore, this study further considers different fixture release timings during cooling and examines the redistribution of deformation and residual stress caused by springback after unclamping.

Therefore, this study takes a typical butt-welded joint of a 6005A aluminum alloy high-speed train sidewall as the research object. A thermo-mechanical finite element model is established to compare free welding, continuous constraint, immediate release, and delayed release conditions, to reveal the effect of fixture release timing on welding deformation and residual stress.

2 Numerical model establishment

To describe the heat input characteristics and temperature field evolution during the butt welding process of high-speed train sidewalls, a welding thermal analysis model was established. The model employs a shell-solid hybrid modeling strategy: solid elements are used for the weld and near-weld areas to ensure the accuracy of calculations for local temperature gradients, plastic deformation, and residual stress; shell elements are used for the skin and internal rib areas far from the weld to improve overall computational efficiency.

A typical local structure of a high-speed train sidewall was selected as the research object. The model dimensions are 300 mm × 320 mm × 30 mm, where the X direction is the weld extension direction, the Y direction is the structural width direction, and the Z direction is the thickness direction. The structure adopts a typical configuration of "upper and lower skins + internal hollow diagonal ribs". The thickness of the upper and lower skins is 4mm, and the thickness of the internal hollow diagonal ribs is 3mm. The specific structure is shown in Figure 1.

Fig. 1: High-speed train sidewall model

The heat source is described using the Goldak double ellipsoidal volume heat source model, and the heat source is moved and loaded along the weld direction through the Abaqus user subroutine DFLUX, as shown in Figure 2.

Fig. 2: Goldak double ellipsoidal heat source model

The formula for the double ellipsoidal heat source model is:

$$q_f(x, y, z) = \frac{6\sqrt{3}f_f Q}{\pi^{3/2}abc_f} \exp \left[-3 \left(\frac{x}{c_f} \right)^2 - 3 \left(\frac{y}{a} \right)^2 - 3 \left(\frac{z}{b} \right)^2 \right]$$

$$q_r(x, y, z) = \frac{6\sqrt{3}f_r Q}{\pi^{3/2}abc_r} \exp \left[-3 \left(\frac{x}{c_r} \right)^2 - 3 \left(\frac{y}{a} \right)^2 - 3 \left(\frac{z}{b} \right)^2 \right]$$

$$Q = \eta UI$$

In the formula, q_f and q_r represent the volumetric heat flux density within the front and rear hemispherical regions, respectively; a is the half-axis in the weld width direction, b is the half-axis in the thickness direction, c_f and c_r are the length half-axis of the front and rear hemispherical regions in the welding direction, respectively; f_f and f_r are the heat distribution coefficients of the front and rear ellipsoids, satisfying $f_f + f_r = 2$; Q is the effective heat input power; U is the welding voltage, I is the welding current, and η is the welding thermal efficiency. Although the present study is mainly based on numerical simulation, the reliability of the adopted model is supported by the physical consistency of the modeling strategy and by parameter selection from established welding simulation practice.

The welding process parameters and the double ellipsoid heat source parameters are shown in the table below:

Table 1: Welding process parameters

Welding voltage (V)	Welding current (A)	Welding speed (mm/s)	Thermal efficiency
18	160	10	0.8

Table 2 Double ellipsoid heat source parameters

a(mm)	b(mm)	c_f (mm)	c_r (mm)	f_f	f_r
4	4	5	10	0.6	1.4

Table 3 Temperature-related performance parameters of 6005A aluminum alloy

Temperature (°C)	25	100	200	400	600
Density(g/cm ³)	2.7	2.68	2.66	2.62	2.57
thermal Conductivity [W/(m · K)]	180.48	185.33	189.53	194.47	197.45
Specific heat capacity [J/(kg · K)]	0.9	0.94	0.99	1.07	1.21
elastic modulus (GPa)	67.54	64.65	60.79	25.4	7
Yield strength (MPa)	210	185	110	30	12
Poisson's ratio	0.33	0.34	0.34	0.35	0.37

To analyze the variation of temperature and stress fields along the width direction near the weld, an observation path perpendicular to the weld was established in the solid element model. The path is located in the stable welding region 150 mm from the weld start point. As shown in Figure 3, the temperature and stress gradients are large near the weld, and decrease rapidly along the direction perpendicular to the weld; after about 15 mm from the weld, the changes tend to level off. Based on this, the weld and the 15 mm range on both sides are divided into solid element regions, and shell elements are used for the remaining regions, as shown in Figure 4, to balance computational accuracy and efficiency. This provides a mechanical basis for using solid elements in the near-weld region and shell elements in the far-field region.

Fig. 3: Comparison of Temperature and Stress Distributions

Fig. 4: Shell-solid hybrid model

3 Operating Condition Design and Evaluation Methods

To investigate the impact of clamp release timing on post-weld deformation and residual stress in the butt weld of the 6005A aluminum alloy sidewall of high-speed train, four welding conditions were established with the same heat input parameters, material properties, and boundary heat transfer conditions: free condition (FC), continuously clamped condition (CC), immediate release condition (IR), and release after cooling to 100°C (TR). In the FC condition, no clamp constraint was applied throughout the welding and cooling process; in the CC condition, the clamp constraint was maintained throughout the process; in the IR condition, the clamp constraint was removed immediately after welding; and in the TR condition, the clamp constraint was removed after the temperature at the monitoring point dropped to 100°C.

Clamp constraints mainly include clamping, positioning, and support constraints. The clamp constraint is used to limit local lifting and out-of-plane warping of the component near the welding area; the positioning constraint is used to suppress overall rigid body displacement of the structure; and the support constraint is used to simulate the supporting effect of the tooling on the component. The clamps were located 90 mm away from the weld on both sides, with a size of 20mm × 40mm, as shown in Figure 5. The only difference between the four working conditions is the method of applying and releasing the clamp constraints; the other modeling conditions remain the same, thus ensuring that the differences in post-weld deformation and residual stress under different working conditions are mainly caused by the fixture release timing.

Fig. 5: Pressing block position

To ensure the comparability of results under different working conditions, the output time and data extraction location were standardized. This paper uses the final stable state after complete cooling and release of corresponding constraints post-weld as the output time, and characterizes post-weld deformation by out-of-plane displacement of the component, while comparing the maximum positive and maximum negative displacements.

Residual stress analysis was performed using a path extraction method. Path 1 is the transverse residual stress extraction path, and Path 2 is the longitudinal residual stress extraction path, used to compare the distribution patterns of residual stress in the weld's vicinity under different working conditions. A temperature monitoring point was located at the weld tail and used to determine the release time of the pressure block under TR conditions. The evaluation locations and path settings are shown in Figure 6.

Fig. 6: Extraction path

4 Results Analysis and Discussion

4.1 Deformation characteristics after welding

To analyze the influence of different clamp release timings on the post-weld deformation of the aluminum alloy sidewall of a high-speed train, out-of-plane displacement U_3 contour plots of the component under four working conditions were extracted, as shown in Figure 7, and their maximum positive and negative displacements were compared. The results show that the post-weld out-of-plane deformation under all four working conditions is mainly concentrated in the weld and its adjacent area, with the displacement gradient gradually decreasing away from the weld. This indicates that localized uneven shrinkage caused by welding heat input is the main source of the component's out-of-plane deformation. The overall deformation morphology of the component is basically consistent under different working conditions, showing obvious negative deflection in the weld area and its adjacent location, while a certain degree of positive warping occurs in areas away from the weld, indicating that the post-weld component's out-of-plane deformation has typical bending and warping characteristics.

Fig. 7: Post-weld displacement contour plot

In terms of maximum positive displacement, the FC, CC, IR, and TR conditions are 0.5493, 0.2362, 0.5315, and 0.5296 mm, respectively, showing a trend of $FC > IR > TR > CC$. Among them, the CC condition has the smallest maximum positive displacement, indicating that the continuous constraint can significantly suppress positive warping deformation of the component. The FC condition has the largest maximum positive displacement, indicating that free warping caused by welding shrinkage is more pronounced under unconstrained conditions. The maximum positive displacements of the IR and TR conditions are between FC and CC, and the difference between them is small, indicating that the release

conditions have only a limited effect on suppressing positive warping, but still weaker than continuous constraint throughout the entire process.

In terms of maximum negative displacement, the FC, CC, IR, and TR conditions are -0.9662, -0.8458, -0.9869, and -0.9824 mm, respectively. Comparing the absolute values, the trend is $IR > TR > FC > CC$. It can be seen that the absolute value of the maximum negative displacement under all four working conditions is significantly greater than the corresponding maximum positive displacement, indicating that the overall out-of-plane deformation of the welded component is mainly U_3 negative deflection, while the positive displacement is mainly manifested as secondary warping in local areas or edge springback. Among them, the CC working condition has the smallest absolute value of the maximum negative displacement, further indicating that the continuous constraint is most effective in suppressing the overall out-of-plane deformation; while the maximum negative displacements of the IR, TR and FC working conditions are relatively close, indicating that the structure underwent significant deformation release and springback after the fixture was released, and its final overall deformation level is similar to that of the free welding working condition.

4.2 Residual stress distribution and release mechanism

To analyze the effect of fixture release timing on residual stress, the longitudinal residual stress along Path 2 and the transverse residual stress along the weld direction were extracted, as shown in Figure 8. Four working conditions, namely FC, CC, IR, and TR, were compared.

Fig. 8: Residual stress distribution

For the longitudinal residual stress, all conditions show a tensile stress peak in the weld center region and lower compressive stress away from the weld, which is a typical distribution pattern in welded structures. The peak longitudinal residual stresses are 206.786 MPa for FC, 242.324 MPa for CC, 217.345 MPa for IR, and 209.858 MPa for TR, with the order $CC > IR > TR > FC$. The CC condition shows the highest peak stress, indicating that continuous constraint suppresses deformation but also limits the release of welding shrinkage, resulting in higher residual stress retention. In contrast, FC shows the lowest peak stress because the structure can deform more freely and thus relieve part of the welding shrinkage. The IR and TR conditions lie between these two cases, and the slightly lower stress in TR suggests that delayed release is more favorable for reducing longitudinal residual stress.

For the transverse residual stress, the four conditions show similar overall trends, but the CC condition still exhibits a clearly higher tensile stress level in the weld region. By comparison, FC, IR, and TR remain relatively low, and IR and TR show similar distributions. This indicates that continuous constraint also increases transverse stress concentration, while fixture release allows transverse shrinkage to be accommodated more sufficiently.

The above differences are related to the mechanical response after unclamping. During welding and cooling, the fixture restrains local bending and shrinkage deformation near the weld, so part of the deformation is temporarily stored in the form of elastic strain. Once the fixture is released, this elastic strain is partially recovered, causing springback and stress redistribution. Therefore, springback after unclamping is essentially a manifestation of elastic recovery.

The difference between IR and TR is mainly due to the thermo-mechanical state at the time of release. Under IR, the fixture is removed immediately after welding, when the weld region is still at high temperature, and the material stiffness is relatively low. As a result, the structure is more sensitive to deformation redistribution, leading to a relatively higher residual stress after cooling. Under TR, the fixture is released after the monitoring point cools to 100°C, when the temperature gradient is lower, and the material stiffness has partially recovered. Therefore, delayed release is more beneficial for reducing peak longitudinal residual stress.

In summary, fixture release timing affects the balance between deformation control and residual stress reduction. Continuous constraint is effective for deformation control but retains higher residual stress, while free welding reduces

residual stress at the cost of larger deformation. Compared with IR, TR provides a better compromise by reducing longitudinal residual stress while maintaining a similar transverse stress level.

5 Conclusion

A shell-solid hybrid finite element model of a butt-welded 6005A aluminum alloy high-speed train sidewall was established. The solid element model and the hybrid element model were compared and analyzed to determine the reasonable division position between solid elements and shell elements. Results show that at a distance of 15 mm from both sides of the weld along the direction perpendicular to the weld, the temperature and stress fields tend to level off. When the distance is greater than 15 mm, the temperature and stress levels are low, and the impact on the thermo-mechanical response of the adjacent area of the weld is small. Therefore, dividing the weld and the 15 mm area on both sides into solid element regions and the remaining areas into shell element regions can improve computational efficiency while ensuring computational accuracy.

Different clamp release timings have a significant impact on out-of-plane deformation and residual stress peak and distribution characteristics after welding. Under all four working conditions, out-of-plane deformation of the component after welding is mainly negative displacement. The continuous constraint condition has the most significant inhibitory effect on out-of-plane deformation after welding. In the release conditions, a certain degree of springback occurs after the clamps are released, and the overall deformation level is similar to that of the free welding condition. Longitudinal residual stresses all exhibit a typical distribution pattern: tensile stress concentration in the weld center region, gradually transforming into compressive stress further away from the weld. The peak values follow the order $CC > IR > TR > FC$. For transverse residual stress, the CC case maintains a higher overall tensile stress level along the weld direction, significantly higher than the other cases.

The timing of fixture release fundamentally alters the distribution relationship between "deformation release" and "stress retention" during welding shrinkage. Continuous constraint helps suppress post-weld deformation but leads to a higher level of residual stress retention; free welding helps reduce residual stress but results in larger overall deformation; immediate and delayed release cases show a trade-off effect, with delayed release being superior to immediate release in reducing longitudinal residual stress while maintaining a similar overall deformation level. This indicates that moderately extending the fixture holding time helps achieve a better balance between post-weld deformation control and residual stress reduction. These findings can provide practical guidance for fixture design and welding process control in industry, especially for improving dimensional accuracy and residual stress management in large-scale thin-walled aluminum alloy structures.

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